

Scaling Under Dynamic Uncertainty Using Laws of Growth

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*produktentwicklung
maschinenelemente*

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Agenda

- **Scaling and Type Range Development**
- **Methods for Scaling – Introduction**
- **Uncertainty Consideration**
 - Application: Example Product
 - Dynamic Uncertainty Laws of Growth
- **Conclusion**

Scaling/Size Range Development

Introduction and definitions

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Scaling is the adaption of a product to different values of specific requirements and the transformation of data from one model's scale to another.

[1], [8], [9]

- Scaling is used in size range development and model theory
- Size range development is according to Pahl/Beitz [1]:

By a size range we refer to technical artefacts [...] that:

- fulfil the same function
- are based on the same solution principle
- are made in varying sizes
- involve similar production processes

Scaling/Size Range Development

Examples for size ranges and scaled properties

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[2]

[3]

Different kinds of
scaling in size
range development

[6]

[5]

following [4]

Methods for Scaling

Introduction

Dimensional Analysis

- Uses nondimensional numbers to represent similarities
- Reduces complexity through nondimensionalization
- Keeping nondimensional numbers constant leads to similar behaviour of the product

$$Re = \frac{L \cdot v \cdot \rho}{\eta}$$

$$Ca = \frac{Ho}{Ne}$$

$$Bi = \frac{h \cdot L}{\lambda}$$

[1], [7]

Laws of Growth [1]

- Use step factors
- Express similarity laws with step factors
- Allow to design new variants of the targeted product properties quickly

$$\phi_{i,j} = \frac{i_j}{i_0} = \frac{1 \text{ mm}}{2 \text{ mm}} = 0,5 \quad \phi_E = 1$$

$$\phi_{costs} = a_3 \phi_l^3 + a_2 \phi_l^2 + a_1 \phi_l + a_0$$

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Methods for Scaling

Advantages & need for research

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Advantages of size range development methodology (LoG)[1]:

- Most of the design work has to be done only **once per size range** → cost savings

Research Question:

How can dynamic uncertainty be taken into consideration when developing a size range using *Laws of Growth*?

Methodology:

- No methods to calculate the impact of dynamic uncertainty with Laws of Growth

Application

Bike disc brake (wear effects)

- Discs available with different diameters (size range)
- Semi-similarity because of interfaces (disc/hub, disc/caliper)
- $\phi_\sigma = 1$ (same utilization of the material)
- Braking reduces the cross section of the disc through abrasion → *strength decreases during usage*
→ **size dependency?**
- The lifetime of the disc is highly affected by uncertainty

Excursion: Uncertainty

Different types of uncertainty [16]:

- Stochastic uncertainty
- Estimated uncertainty
- Unknown uncertainty

Dynamic uncertainty depends from time or load cycles.

[10]

Application

Deriving LoG for dynamic uncertainty

simplification $\rightarrow \phi_\sigma = \frac{\phi_F}{\phi_A} = 1$

$$\phi_A = f(t, N, c_{cor}(t), F_B, A_B, v)$$

$$\phi_A = f(\phi_N(t), \phi_{c_{cor}}(t), \phi_{F_B}, \phi_{A_B}, \phi_v)$$

$$1 = \frac{\phi_F}{\phi_A}$$

static uncertainty

dynamic uncertainty

t = time

c_{corr} = corrosion rate

A_B = area of brake pad

N = revolutions (wheel, braking)

F_B = brake force on capiler

v = rel. speed of brake pad to disc

Application

Computing the product's behaviour

i =input parameter, o =output parameter

Conclusion

Dynamic uncertainty quantification with LoG

- Quantification of size and time dependent uncertainty in size range development is possible
- Leads to better knowledge about product
- Less safety margin needed/higher level of safety achieved
- Categorisation of methods done

Thank you for your attention!

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